

Apêndice B: Lista de estudos excluídos após leitura na íntegra.

Título	Ano	Motivo da exclusão
A Cluster-randomized Trial to Evaluate the Efficacy of Wolbachia-Infected Aedes Aegypti Mosquitoes in Reducing the Incidence of Arboviral Infection in Brazil (EVITA Dengue)	2020	Desenho do estudo incompatível
Field deployment of wMel and wMelpop Wolbachia infections in Aedes aegypti field populations to block dengue transmission in Australia and Vietnam	2013	Desenho do estudo incompatível
Wolbachia infections of Aedes aegypti and their potential to control dengue transmission	2011	Desenho do estudo incompatível
THE DENGUE STOPPER.	2015	Desenho do estudo incompatível
The use of Wolbachia by the World Mosquito Program to interrupt transmission of Aedes Aegypti transmitted viruses	2018	Desenho do estudo incompatível
Advances in vector control science: Rear-and-release strategies show promise... but don't forget the basics	2017	Desenho do estudo incompatível
Evaluación de las estrategias innovadoras para el control de Aedes aegypti: desafíos para su introducción y evaluación del impacto	2019	Desenho do estudo incompatível
Cost of dengue vector control: Systematic literature review	2014	Desenho do estudo incompatível
Wolbachia for dengue control; Will dengue viruses evolve resistance?	2017	Desenho do estudo incompatível
Trends in dengue research in the Philippines: A systematic review	2019	Desenho do estudo incompatível
The cost-effectiveness of controlling dengue in Indonesia using wMel Wolbachia released at scale: a modelling study	2020	Desenho do estudo incompatível
Cost-effectiveness of Wolbachia to reduce dengue burden in major Indonesian cities	2019	Desenho do estudo incompatível
Refining estimates of dengue virus transmission potential in wild type and wMel-infected Aedes aegypti: Field rearing conditions alter virus susceptibility	2016	Desenho do estudo incompatível
Role of the vector in arbovirus transmission	2014	Desenho do estudo incompatível
The impact of large-scale deployment of Wolbachia mosquitoes on arboviral disease incidence in Rio de Janeiro and Niterói, Brazil: study protocol for a controlled interrupted time series analysis using routine disease surveillance data	2019	Desenho do estudo incompatível
Using Wolbachia to eliminate dengue: Will the virus fight back?	2021	Desenho do estudo incompatível
Modeling the impact on virus transmission of Wolbachia-mediated blocking of dengue virus infection of Aedes aegypti	2015	Desenho do estudo incompatível
Stability of the wMel Wolbachia Infection following Invasion into Aedes aegypti Populations	2016	Desenho do estudo incompatível
Bacteria and antiviral immunity in insects.	2015	Desenho do estudo incompatível

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Establishment of a Wolbachia Superinfection in Aedes aegypti Mosquitoes as a Potential Approach for Future Resistance Management	2016	Desenho do estudo incompatível
The economic impact and cost-effectiveness of combined vector-control and dengue vaccination strategies in Thailand: Results from a dynamic transmission model	2020	Desenho do estudo incompatível
Reducing dengue fever cases at the lowest budget: a constrained optimization approach applied to Thailand.	2021	Desenho do estudo incompatível
Stable introduction of a life-shortening Wolbachia infection into the mosquito Aedes aegypti	2009	Desenho do estudo incompatível
When a bacterium fights arboviruses	2019	Desenho do estudo incompatível
Applying Wolbachia to Eliminate Dengue	2017	Desenho do estudo incompatível
Growing evidence that the world mosquito program's wolbachia method reduces dengue transmission	2019	Estudo indisponível
Composition of the Aedes aegypti microbiome is altered by wolbachia, but is not critical to wolbachia blocking of dengue virus	2018	Estudo indisponível
Erratum: Using Wolbachia to eliminate dengue: will the virus fight back?	2021	Estudo indisponível
Correction for Edenborough et al., "Using Wolbachia to Eliminate Dengue: Will the Virus Fight Back?".	2021	Estudo indisponível
Biological control of mosquito-borne diseases: The potential of wolbachia-based interventions in an IVM framework	2018	Sem desfecho de interesse
Vector population manipulation for control of arboviruses--a novel prospect for India.	2014	Sem desfecho de interesse
Establishment of wMel Wolbachia in Aedes aegypti mosquitoes and reduction of local dengue transmission in Cairns and surrounding locations in northern Queensland, Australia	2019	Sem desfecho de interesse
A review: Aedes-borne arboviral infections, controls and wolbachia-based strategies	2021	Sem desfecho de interesse
Towards integrated management of dengue in Mumbai	2021	Sem desfecho de interesse
Papel de la bacteria endosimbionte Wolbachia en el control de enfermedades vectoriales: dengue, zika y chikunkunya	2017	Sem desfecho de interesse
A greener vision for vector control: The example of the singapore dengue control programme	2020	Sem desfecho de interesse
Las enfermedades transmitidas por vectores y el potencial uso de Wolbachia, una bacteria endocelular obligada, para erradicarlas	2017	Sem desfecho de interesse
Enfrentamento ao Aedes Aegypti no contexto brasileiro	2019	Sem desfecho de interesse
Combating mosquito-borne diseases using genetic control technologies	2021	Sem desfecho de interesse
Wolbachia-Associated Bacterial Protection in the Mosquito Aedes aegypti	2013	Sem desfecho de interesse
Complex wolbachia infection dynamics in mosquitoes with imperfect maternal transmission.	2018	Sem desfecho de interesse
The microbiome composition of Aedes aegypti is not critical for Wolbachia-mediated inhibition of dengue virus	2017	Sem desfecho de interesse

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The endosymbiotic bacterium Wolbachia induces resistance to dengue virus in <i>Aedes aegypti</i>	2010	Sem desfecho de interesse
Embryonic development and egg viability of wMel-infected <i>Aedes aegypti</i>	2019	Sem desfecho de interesse
Avaliação da influência da Wolbachia na infecção e transmissão vertical do vírus dengue em mosquitos <i>Aedes aegypti</i>	2015	Sem desfecho de interesse
Large-Scale Deployment and Establishment of Wolbachia Into the <i>Aedes aegypti</i> Population in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil	2021	Sem desfecho de interesse
Genetic stability of <i>Aedes aegypti</i> populations following invasion by wMel Wolbachia	2021	Sem desfecho de interesse
Stable establishment of WMEL wolbachia in <i>aedes aegypti</i> populations in Yogyakarta, Indonesia	2020	Sem desfecho de interesse
Local introduction and heterogeneous spatial spread of dengue-suppressing Wolbachia through an urban population of <i>Aedes aegypti</i>	2017	Sem desfecho de interesse